

Reflection in action: a critical reflection tool to help students deal with uncertainties in designing solutions for complex problems

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ABSTRACT

At Delft University of Technology (DUT) in the Netherlands, multi-disciplinary teams of students collaborate with professionals in living labs to design solutions for real-life complex problems in technological innovation processes. Students are guided by a lecturer through the four phases of design to “cut through” the complexity of the problem. However, in these 'ill-defined wicked problems' nobody has an overall picture of the problem and students face many uncertainties. These uncertainties are often perceived as a barrier for decision-making within the design process.

A reflection tool, based on theoretical insights in transformative and triple-loop learning, is developed to help students critically reflect in action, providing them with options to deal with their uncertainties. We distinguish between task, social, and individual uncertainty. In this study, the central question is: How can the reflection tool help students deal with their uncertainties in solving complex problems in DUT living labs. By means of surveys and interviews we monitored students in two living labs, one with bachelor and one with master students. We focused on what kind of uncertainties they encountered, how they dealt with these uncertainties and how the reflection tool supports them in this regard.

Analysis of the data shows that students perceived all types of uncertainty in the various phases of the design process. By means of the reflection tool students gradually became aware of the many options they have in dealing with uncertainties, and particularly how these pertain to their decision-making in the design process.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Problem

Major socio-technical problems require that many people from different disciplines, angles, and expertise generate new knowledge and solutions together. Living labs have been set up at Delft University of Technology to integrate complex problem-solving in higher education. In the living labs, students work together with academics and professionals. In the minor and master program of Communication Design for Innovation at TU Delft, this is done in the so-called 'C-Labs'. In this, teams of multi-disciplinary students work together with a commissioner and stakeholders (professionals) to analyse and design for complex socio-technical problems. Students do this according to the design-based learning methodology, under the supervision of a lecturer and student teaching assistants.

With these ill-defined, so called 'wicked' problems, neither the students, commissioner, stakeholders or lecturer has a clear view of the problem or what to design for. Following the design process, the actual problem and subsequent design emerges from the collaboration between the different actors. Wherein the commissioner and stakeholders provide in-depth content knowledge, and the lecturer knowledge concerning systems (thinking), collaboration and decision making. The lecturer also provides tools for design and facilitates the process. It is up to the students to combine these different inputs in order to make design decisions. Decisions that on one hand must take into account the design process, and on the other the needs and wishes of their commissioner and stakeholders. This causes students to face a lot of uncertainty, which can be a barrier for their decision-making, and subsequently, their learning process.

1.2 Research goal and question

Since uncertainty is inherent to learning, it is not the intention to resolve or remove uncertainties in the C-labs, but rather to teach students how to deal with uncertainty to prevent that it negatively influences their decision-making and learning process. For that, we started a two-year study (funded by the 4TU Centre of Engineering Education in the Netherlands) with the aim of gaining insight into how students can be supported in solving complex problems in living labs.

Part of the research project is specifically aimed at critical reflection and is divided into three phases: In the first phase, the focus is on the question: To what extent do students experience uncertainties and how do they deal with them? The second phase focuses on the question: How can a critical reflection tool help students with this? and in the final phase, the question is: How can the tool be embedded in living labs such as the C-lab?

In this paper we will discuss the first two phases. The overarching question of this paper is: How can the reflection tool help students deal with their uncertainties in solving complex problems in DUT living labs?

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 The C-lab

The concept of the C-labs is based on **authentic learning** and **design-based learning** (DBL). Authentic learning is learning by being involved in real-world problem solving [1]. DBL is described by Gomez Punte, van Eijck, & Jochems [2] as “an educational approach where students gather and apply theoretical knowledge to solve design problems” and rooted in “active learning methods that facilitate

students' learning processes" (p.14). Within C-labs, design-based learning is used to approach the problems in a structured way; a creative, disciplined and decision-oriented inquiry, carried out in iterative cycles. Basically, DBL is a teaching approach similar to, and often compared with, problem-based learning; however, in DBL the design process is of main importance. The iterative cycles in design-based learning follow the four stages of the double diamond: discover, define, develop, and deliver [10].

A crucial skill in design-based learning, due to its decision-oriented inquiry nature, is **coping with uncertainty** [3]. We distinguish **three types of uncertainty** that can inhibit the decision-making process of students in design-based learning [4] [5]. First, task uncertainty, wherein the uncertainty is caused by a lack of overview of information necessary or the complexity of the task. Second, social uncertainty, wherein uncertainty is caused by a lack of necessary information exchange or collaborative action. Within social uncertainty we distinguish uncertainty attributed to fellow students, lecturer, and commissioner. The third type is individual uncertainty, wherein uncertainty is caused by a perceived lack of competence of the individual student.

2.2 Critical reflection

As dealing with uncertainty requires students to become aware of how they experience it, it seems necessary for students **to critically reflect** on their uncertain experiences within their learning process. Given this design-based learning process involves many actors from different (technological) backgrounds: diverse students, professionals and lecturer, everyone can perceive uncertainty differently. This research therefore holds a **constructivist view on learning**, seen as using previous interpretations to construct new interpretations of the meaning of one's experience. Both transformative learning [6] [7] and triple-loop learning [8] follow this constructivist view and focus on critical reflection to achieve transformation [7] [8] or profound change [8]. Both theories indicate various levels on which an individual might reflect to deal with a mismatch or disjunction with their current way of viewing the situation. Daalhuizen et al. refer to these situations as non-routine situations wherein the individual experiences uncertainty in the decision-making process [5]. This also warrants a focus on the type of reflection, where this research looks at both reflection in-action: reflecting while doing to change the current situation, and reflection on-action: retrospective reflection to influence future situations [9].

2.3 Perspective Pyramid

This research integrates the above-mentioned theories into a framework for an individual's perspective on which an individual might reflect to become aware of and deal with experienced uncertainty. The framework, called **perspective pyramid** (see figure 1), is grounded in one's perception of knowledge (epistemology), reality (metaphysics) and value (axiology). At the bottom of the pyramid lies one's *frame of reference* - the structure of cultural and psychological assumptions which assimilates past and shapes future experiences. One's frame of reference comprises *habits of mind* - ways of feeling, acting, and thinking based on previous assumptions, which is shown as the second layer from the bottom. One layer above holds the *points of view*, which express the habits of mind. These are constellations of beliefs, feelings, attitudes, and judgments. These are further comprised of *meaning scheme clusters* (the layer above), sets of immediate specific expectations, beliefs, feelings, attitudes,

and judgments. The top layer is then one's *interpretation* of reality – the culmination of the layers into how one experiences a situation.

The perspective pyramid is operationalised as a critical reflection tool used to reflect in-action while students experience uncertainty, by taking the following steps, see figure 1. First, students are asked to classify their uncertainty (task, social, or individual uncertainty). Second, students use the reflection tool to critically ask themselves why they are experiencing uncertainty, going through the different layers of the pyramid from top to bottom. Third, having identified their uncertainty, students are asked to generate options for decision-making in dealing with their uncertainty. The tool was implemented as a paper booklet in phase 2 (see 3.2 Methodology).

Fig. 1: Example of reflection tool in use

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Phase 1

The focus of the first phase was to explore to what extent students experience uncertainties and how they deal with them. In this study, 35 BSc students participated, who all signed the consent form. The students had a wide variety of technical backgrounds, where most came from computer science, mechanical engineering, architecture, and industrial design. Criteria for group composition were based on students' bachelor programs: every team consisted of students with different backgrounds. The students worked in teams of 4-7 and each team focused on a different case; all complex socio-technical problems from practice. The cases were submitted by government, industry and non-profit organizations. These professionals ("commissioners") were actively involved during the entire process, from problem definition to the presentation of the final product. They were available

for input and feedback; at set times and when students had specific questions. The minor included 8 cases with 8 student teams, spread across 9 commissioners. The C-lab course (15 ECTS) took one semester (September 2021 – February 2022). Students worked on the case from day one. The lectures and supervision by the lecturer and student assistants were aimed at getting students to go through the design process in a systematic way, as explained in section 2.1 of this paper. During the course students filled out weekly surveys with open- and closed-ended questions. The survey asked participants to reflect on which type of uncertainty they experienced that week, how they dealt with it, and what they would need to deal with such uncertainty throughout the design process. All data was anonymised, and the mentioned uncertainties were coded via pre- and open coding and divided into three categories: uncertainty attributed to the individual, the social context and the task. Additional measurements were used to specify and interpret the data from the weekly student-surveys, like introductory and final student surveys, learning style assessments, and interviews with lecturer and commissioners. Due to the limited size of this paper, this is not discussed in detail here.

3.2 Phase 2

The focus of the second phase was to validate the reflection pyramid as a tool. Four MSc students, all with different technological backgrounds, participated in this part of the research. They took part in a C-lab project in an international context that was compressed in one full week (November 2021). The students filled out daily reflection booklets in which the perspective pyramid was integrated (see figure 1). First students reflected on each type of uncertainty (task, social, individual). Next, each type of uncertainty experienced was further reflected on, using the layers of the perspective pyramid. Lastly students were prompted to formulate potential follow-up actions with respect to their reflections on uncertainty. Students filled out the booklet individually at the end of each day, in a facilitated reflection session.

Retrospective semi-structured interviews on basis of the reflection booklets were held with each individual student: questions related to their process and output of the week, their use and experience of the reflection tool, their awareness and ways of dealing with uncertainty, and possible improvements to the reflection tool. The 4 interviews with master students in this second phase of the research were transcribed and coded via open coding.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Phase 1

In the monitored living lab with bachelor students, all types of uncertainty were reported. Task uncertainty, social uncertainty regarding collaboration and communication with fellow students, lecturer, and commissioner, and individual uncertainty, see figure 2. Throughout the course, task uncertainty was the most prevalent, and fellow students and lecturer uncertainty were mentioned the least. Individual uncertainty was reported more often, peaking in week 13, where students indicated they were stuck in the design process.

Fig. 2: Perceived uncertainty types throughout C-Lab

To some extent, students were aware of the **causes of their uncertainty**, which changes throughout the course. In weeks 2-4 (discover phase) the cause of uncertainty among most of the students was associated with an unclear task, goal, or unclear next steps to take. They attributed their task uncertainty with causes outside themselves. In weeks 4-7 (define phase), they perceived the cause of their uncertainty having more to do with difficulties in their communication with the commissioners and stakeholders. From week 11 onwards (develop and deliver phases), students took more ownership in dealing with the complexity of the case, basing their decision-making on integrating different perspectives from stakeholders and their commissioner. This required actively asking practitioners critical questions in a practice that is new to most students, causing both task and social uncertainty. Moreover, the introductory survey and interviews with the lecturer showed that bachelor students have little experience with critical reflection, and a limited critical mindset.

“Students struggle with developing a critical mindset, to accept different perspectives.” (lecturer)

Students reflected on what they would need to **deal with** their experienced **uncertainty** in continuation of the course. In the first phase of the design process, the following options were mentioned: better task description, clearer goals, (clearer) stakeholder input, better communication with commissioner and stakeholders. These options for improvement all seem to be attributed external to the student. In the later phases of the design process, students suggested more internally attributed options to deal with their uncertainty. The following options were mentioned: improving communication, be open-minded, take initiative, ask for help, improve teamwork. The weekly reflections of students showed that they gradually took ownership of dealing with their uncertainty.

4.2 Phase 2

Results from the retrospective interviews with master students regarding the use of the reflection tool indicate to what extent the tool supports students in dealing with their uncertainties.

In **using the tool**, students were aware of their uncertainties and it supported them in gaining insights into dealing with their uncertainties as learning opportunities.

When being asked how a student experienced task uncertainty, she mentioned she

had difficulty trusting the design process, finding it difficult to embrace the fuzziness of design. When asked how she reflected on this uncertainty she mentioned:

“The more often you convince yourself it is part of the process, the more it becomes a baseline for yourself. From conscious to subconscious.” (#1)

One student mentioned he was very judgmental to his teammates in the beginning of the process. By using the reflection tool, he mentioned the following regarding social uncertainty:

“The tool made me less judgmental to others, first trying to find out how I project things onto others.” (#2)

When being asked about how the reflection tool contributed to his learning process, one student replied:

“When you become aware of how input fits in your frame of reference, everything becomes a learning opportunity.” (#2)

Students indicated which **conditions** should be prevalent in dealing with uncertainty. The necessity of reflection and reflective discourse was recognized by all students. Two students remarked it especially helped them deal with individual uncertainty. Furthermore, all students were adamant about the importance of creating “common ground” within the respective teams, meaning they had a sense of bonding on a personal and professional level.

“You can reach common ground on both personal and professional level. It can be superficial or deep.” (#3)

When asked how to create common ground the following aspects were mentioned: open-minded attitude, sharing vulnerabilities, shared social and informal activities, time and effort to form bonds. Two students mentioned that having common ground helped them to leave their comfort zone.

“Leaving your comfort zone, to not be afraid but open to new things.” (#2)

Finally, students provided **recommendations** for improving the reflection tool. In reviewing the reflection tool, all students expressed enthusiasm in exploring the lower layers of their pyramid:

“It helped me to think about things I would otherwise not think about.” (#4)

“I quickly kept asking myself how to get to the bottom of the pyramid. This gave me individual insights.” (#2)

This speaks to how the tool facilitates critical reflection through structural questioning. However, they also stressed the importance of how the tool had to be flexible enough to fit individual reflection styles.

“The tool should stimulate reflection in your own way.” (#4)

5 CONCLUSION

The central question of this paper was: How can the reflection tool help students deal with their uncertainties in solving complex problems in DUT living labs? This research shows uncertainty is present throughout the design process in DUT living labs. Results from phase 1 show that systematic reflection helps students take ownership of the causes of their uncertainty and internalise options in dealing with their uncertainty. The critical reflection tool tested in phase 2 had similar results. Moreover, the tool stimulated relatively deeper reflection, providing insights and learning opportunities regarding students' habits of mind and frame of reference. Finally, retrospective interviews about the use of the reflection tool indicated certain conditions and recommendations for dealing with uncertainty in living labs.

6 DISCUSSION

Use of the reflection tool can admittedly lead to insights among students about the more personal 'lower layers of their perspective', but (behavioural) changes cannot always be realized within the context of the living lab. This is why attention should also be paid to critical reflection and personal development in other subjects in the students' curriculum, although dealing with uncertainties may play a less prominent role there.

The retrospective interviews with students indicated their desire for a personalised reflection tool. In phase 3 of this research project, our aim is to develop the reflection tool further to both maintain its structural and critical nature, while also being flexible enough to accommodate personal reflection styles.

The extent to which deeper reflection occurs and helps students deal with their uncertainties has been further researched, and will be discussed during the presentation of this study at SEFI 2022.

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